

IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND SERVICE LIFE OF FLOORS IN INDUSTRIAL AND RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

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At present, the issue of improving the quality and service life of industrial and civil floors has become particularly relevant. In most cases, floors are in an unsatisfactory condition despite the great variety of construction materials and installation technologies. The main defects and damages are: impermissible vertical deformations; the presence of through and surface cracks; scaling (raveling) of the concrete surface layer; the occurrence of potholes; surface unevenness; destruction of temperature-shrinkage joints; and the appearance of the curling effect. A number of causes have been identified:

1. Lack of modern building codes for the design, installation, and repair of high-strength floors. As a result, structural solutions, material selection, and technologies are used without proper engineering and regulatory support. In such cases, the main decision-making criteria become the contractor's prior experience and the customer's cost constraints.
2. Insufficient or no attention to evaluating the properties of the concrete base, as well as a mismatch between actual service loads and the design calculations of the load-bearing capacity of the structure. At the same time, excessive emphasis is placed on the materials of the finishing surface layer and the technologies for its installation.
3. Low concrete quality and insufficient control on site. Test results of concrete specimens confirm discrepancies between actual and declared strength values.
4. Using compressive strength as the principal strength characteristic for concrete, although for floor structures this indicator is secondary; the key indicators are direct tensile strength and flexural tensile strength.
5. Unjustified selection of materials used to harden the concrete surface layer, without accounting for the quantitative values of abrasive loads on the floor. The absence of a unified method for assessing concrete surface wear indices prevents an objective comparison and selection of the material required for specified service loads.
6. Non-compliance with construction technology (workmanship).
7. Loads exceeding the design values, or even those specified by standards.

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